

Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

WP5

Mainstreaming the Research Career Framework

Deliverable 5.2

Mainstreaming Plan for SECURE Research Career Framework

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full name
BHO	EURAXESS Bridgehead Organisation, national EURAXESS network coordinator
BZN	Bay Zoltán Nonprofit Ltd. for Applied Research (SECURE partner)
COST	European Cooperation in Science and Technology
CoARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
ESCO	European Skills, Competences and Occupations classification
Eurodoc	The European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Young Researchers (SECURE partner)
ICoRSA	International Consortium of Research Staff Associations (SECURE partner)
MCAA	Marie Curie Alumni Association (SECURE partner)
RCF	SECURE Research Career Framework
RESAVER	Retirement Savings Vehicle European pension plan for researchers
RFO	Research funding organisation
RPO	Research performing organisation
YERUN	Young European Research Universities Network (SECURE partner)

Explanations and state of play

The **SECURE Mainstreaming Plan** is a tool to disseminate and exploit the results of the SECURE project, most notably the Research Career Framework (RCF) [3], involving the whole SECURE consortium for strategic stakeholder engagement. Accordingly, the Plan provides a schedule and list of targeted engagement and exploitation activities, specifying the target group, the focus point(s) of the RCF to be used, the activity type, the responsible SECURE partner, the timing and the key performance indicators for each activity. The aim of the Mainstreaming Plan is to help potential users to get informed about, get to know the details of, and receive tailored tips for applying the RCF for their own purposes. It includes activities both before and beyond the project lifetime to drive the take-up of the RCF, with a time span optimised to the availability of both the SECURE project results and the resources provided by the SECURE consortium.

The **SECURE Research Career Framework (RCF)** is a matrix of actions, structured around 8 thematic pillars, offering support for organisations to improve and support the careers of their researchers and therefore reduce the precarity of research careers. The RCF builds on existing European policy recommendations, such as the **European Framework for Research Careers** and the revised **European Charter for Researchers** [1], aiming to improve the employability of researchers in Europe and make European research careers more attractive. The RCF includes concrete proposals on how to translate the policy recommendations into concrete actions by both research performing organisations (RPOs) and research funding organisations (RFOs). In doing so, the RCF systematizes the numerous recommendations of the policy documents addressing the core topic of each, describing their relevance and scope for RPOs/RFOs and providing internal cross-references to other relevant recommendations for a better overview.

While the RCF is directly relevant for various types of European RPOs and RFOs, considerable effort is still required by these institutions to internalise and implement the actions relevant for them in a meaningful way, aiming for impact. It is this complex process that the SECURE Mainstreaming Plan is setting out to help, providing an initial, detailed encounter between the RCF and potentially interested stakeholders representing a wide variety of European institutions employing or funding researchers. Where relevant, the experience of SECURE trial organisations, which have already completed the exercise of piloting and implementing relevant actions of the RCF, will be provided as practical examples within the engagement process.

Planned actions are presented in detail in the key section “**Action plan for mainstreaming the Research Career Framework**” (see below).

The proposed actions in the Mainstreaming Plan cover the period February – July 2025, with the schedule based on the following key dates and outputs of the SECURE project:

Availability of deliverables D2.2 (Report on consultation on SECURE Research Career Framework), D3.2 (Report on consultation on SECURE Tenure Track-Like Models), D4.2 (Report on Trials to Implement SECURE Research Career Framework)	December 2024
Availability of deliverables D 2.3 (Final SECURE Research Career Framework), D3.3 (Final SECURE Tenure Track-Like Models)	January 2025
Availability of deliverable D5.3 (Policy Briefs Promoting SECURE Research Career Framework), organisation of the SECURE Summit and Policy Roundtable event	March 2025
End of SECURE project	31 March 2025

Stakeholder identification

The core of the present Mainstreaming Plan is to plan and deliver actions targeting main stakeholders and offering them insight into how the RCF may be relevant and useful to them. Two sources are used for the initial segmentation of stakeholders: the SECURE Exploitation Plan (D7.2, section 3.2) [6] and the RCF itself.

Building on the SECURE Exploitation Plan, the following stakeholder groups have been identified for the Mainstreaming Plan:

- **Research organisations:** actors employing and funding researchers. They are the primary targets of the Mainstreaming Plan and their interest and willingness in implementing actions from the RCF will directly impact the careers of their employees, including researchers.
- **Multipliers** (EURAXESS BHOs, university networks, umbrella organisations, thematic clusters, project consortia): actors responsible for advocating, informing and assisting research organisations in making research careers less precarious and therefore more attractive to employees. Multipliers also include networks of RPOs which coordinate their activities along principles or topics relevant for research careers (such as EU-funded projects, advocacy or mutual interest topics, regional or broader interest groups etc.) Multipliers may significantly contribute to the dissemination of the RCF and through pooling their members’ resources they may contribute to a more effective implementation of the framework (through sharing members’ experiences or expertise, for example).
- **Policy makers:** actors responsible for the policy agenda, be it regional, national or European, which affects the environment that the research institutions operate in as well as the employment and career conditions of the researchers employed.
- **Researchers:** through advocacy or decision-making roles in their own institutions or in multiplier organisations, researchers may also influence how the RCF is used and mainstreamed. Consequently, in SECURE researchers have been provided consultation instances (a workshop and a survey) to be able to express their opinion on and suggest amendments to, the RCF before its finalisation.

The RCF builds on **two main stakeholder groups**, both of which are included among the SECURE trial organisations: Research Performing Organisations and Research Funding Organisations (both included in the category of “research organisations” above). As the principles analysed in the RCF have a primarily institutional focus, implementing the RCF also has to focus strongly on the institutions and, consequently, this fact informs the actions proposed in the action plan.

Using the Research Career Framework

The Research Career Framework for institutional change

The first main stakeholder group that is envisaged to use the SECURE RCF are European research organisations. Indeed, the RCF primarily caters for uptake by organisations; that is, the systematic use of the RCF in institutional processes aiming at improving the conditions in which researchers work. Thus, the structure of the RCF follows that of the **European Framework for Research Careers**, of which there are 44, grouped in 8 pillars (thematic categories). As annexes, the document also includes an exemplary **list of occupations for researchers** (Annex 1, corresponding to Recommendations 5 and 6) and a new **Charter for Researchers** (Annex 2, corresponding to Recommendation 36). Matching the recommendations in Pillar 4 (Researchers Skilled for Intersectoral and Interdisciplinary Careers and for Entrepreneurship and Innovation), the EC has launched the **European Competence Framework for Researchers** (ResearchComp, corresponding to Recommendation 17) [2], with the aim of offering employers a cross-sectorally relevant toolbox to use in working with researchers’ competences and through this to support the inter-sectoral skills assessment activities relevant for researchers.

The RCF systematically addresses the core topic of each recommendation and notes overlaps and redundancies with other recommendations. For each recommendation, 6 key questions are asked:

- How could this recommendation be relevant and useful for RPOs and RFOs?
- Which principles of the Charter could be relevant for this recommendation?
- How could ResearchComp and ESCO be relevant for this recommendation?
- How could this recommendation reduce the precarity of research careers?
- Which actions could implement this recommendation at RPOs and RFOs?
- Which challenges could hinder this recommendation at RPOs and RFOs?

By the uptake of the RCF we mean getting familiar with the text in order to use it in a critical way in the development of institutional reflections, requests, and actions towards advancing researchers’ working conditions. On the level of individual researchers, the aim of this exercise is to assist more and more researchers getting involved in the shaping of the future European Research Area along the objectives expressed by the policy priorities.

Thus, building on both the policy recommendations and the proposals for their implementation included in the RCF, we suggest one or more of the following simple scenarios to institutions to start working on tailor-made actions:

- **Facilitated reflection** on the RCF to create actions (e.g. by workshops, focus groups, surveys)
- **Institutional needs analysis** (by a consultation process or in the frame of strategic planning, e.g. in line with updating the institutional strategy)
- Alignment with **parallel institutional processes** (e.g. HR Excellence Award, Gender Equality or Diversity Plan, etc.)

More recommendations will soon become available within the SECURE consultation (see project deliverable D2.2) and the RCF implementation trials (see project deliverable D4.2).

The Research Career Framework for advocacy

In addition to research organisations, the Mainstreaming Plan also provides opportunities for individual researchers, especially to those involved in decision-making and advisory roles at any level in research institutions, to support their greater engagement in the process of reforming the EU Research and Innovation sector by facilitating the understanding and accessibility of concrete areas and opportunities of improvement. As a basis of this process, the RCF needs to be communicated and its thorough understanding needs to be facilitated. The following overview may be helpful in this.

As an introduction, basic information needs to be provided to researchers who may not already be involved in science for policy or advocacy and thus may not be acquainted with the legal framework of the European Union. This introduction also needs to present the European Framework for Research Careers and an overview of the SECURE RCF.

Similarly, information on policies and actors will support researchers who are new to advocacy at the EU level in understanding a) the policy documents that in the past years built the context for the Council Recommendation and b) the recognised actors of the ERA and their interplay in the European Union.

Researchers who are already knowledgeable in science for policy and advocacy, may then be offered details of the RCF, in which the 44 recommendations are grouped on the basis of the type of the targeted actor. This way, researchers may learn about alternatives of how to use the recommendations in case they are promoting the uptake of the Recommendation at the institutional level, at local, regional or national level, or at the European level.

In the multi-actor context that characterises the institutional decision-making in the European Research Area, researchers can play an important role at different levels. They can advocate within their own institutions; they can advance their requests to local and national stakeholder organisations in their member state; they can participate in EU consultations. These actors, in one way or the other, exert a strong influence over various aspects of the professional (and, indirectly, private) life of researchers. Our suggestion to researchers, therefore, is to study and understand what stakeholders influencing researchers' professional activities are active in the respective country and institution, followed by the actors active at the EU level.

Building on the implementation trials in SECURE

The SECURE project also foresaw a process for the institutional implementation of the recommendations within the RCF. In this process, the first draft of the RCF (Deliverable D 2.1) was used by six trial organisations, four of which are RPOs, one an RFO, and one a career management company, to co-create their own action plans aiming to implement relevant recommendations of the RCF. The trial organisations have each selected and interpreted a number of actions to make up their individual action plans, via a four-step process. The action plans all follow a centrally defined template structured into six sections. The completion of the institutional actions is also foreseen during the lifetime of the SECURE project and the entire process is summarised in the forthcoming deliverable D4.2. This report on the trials will provide useful instances and lessons on how the organisations approached the planning, implementation and evaluation phases, which may be used as valuable input for any organisation contemplating a similar process based on the RCF in the future.

Action plan for mainstreaming the Research Career Framework

Target stakeholder group	Which part of the RCF?	Activity type	Responsible partner	When?	KPIs	Remarks
EURAXESS member RPOs (660+), including EURAXESS hubs	Sections relevant for mobility and career development	Open webinar for institutions	BZN	First semester 2025	One webinar 50+ RPOs attending	
		Open webinar for researchers	BZN	First semester 2025	One webinar 50+ researchers attending	
		Bilateral engagement sessions with BHOs (as multipliers)	BZN with EURAXESS BHOs	March 2025	Five online discussions Five BHOs attending, reaching out to 100+ EURAXESS member RPOs	Engagement sought for at least one multiplier activity to be done by each BHO
		Info session at the EURAXESS BHO meeting (for all BHOs)	BZN	June 2025	One hybrid session 40 BHO representatives attending from 40 countries	
HR Excellence implementing RPOs (740+)	Sections relevant for organisational support for research careers	Webinar/online session for implementing institutions	BZN	First semester 2025	One webinar 40+ RPOs attending	Feasibility to be checked with the EC as responsible for the HR Excellence process
Other RPOs, including RESAVER members and non-universities	Decide based on national priorities	Webinar/online session	BZN through RESAVER	First semester 2025		Feasibility to be checked with the EC as responsible for RESAVER
University networks (SECURE partners + EUA, The Guild, Coimbra Group etc.)	Sections relevant for organisational support for research careers	Network events	BZN with Eurodoc MCAA YERUN	First semester 2025	Three sessions in three network events 100+ participants reached	1. Session in the Eurodoc Annual Conference 2. Panel/Q&A within MCAA Annual Conference, Krakow 3. YERUN Anniversary event
		Targeted webinars on RCF for ECRs	Eurodoc ICoRSA	First semester 2025	One webinar for associations representing researchers, researcher organizations and unions	Development of support for selfassessment of ECRs, linking the RCF to other competence frameworks designed by the EC and CoE
		Webinar	ICoRSA	First semester 2025	One webinar for Researcher Organizations and Unions	

Target stakeholder group	Which part of the RCF?	Activity type	Responsible partner	When?	KPIs	Remarks
Other stakeholders (RFO, umbrella orgs, research managers)	Sections relevant for research management activities	Communication with the RM ROADMAP and CARDEA projects	CPN	March 2025	One document 20+ project participant organisations reached	
Clusters and consortia (relevant Horizon and Erasmus+ projects)	In line with cluster and project priorities	Communication with the consortia and with DocTalent4EU	CPN	March 2025	One document 40+ project participant organisations reached	Target: FOREU1 and FOREU2 consortia / FOREU4ALL Community of Practice (64 European University Alliance projects)
Policy makers (national and European)	Entire RCF	SECURE Summit event	BZN	March 2025	One event 70+ high-level stakeholders (including policy makers) attending	Participation in exploitation session with stakeholders
COST Association and COST Beneficiaries	Entire RCF	Working group discussion within the COST CCA on Career Development of Young Researchers	BZN, Eurodoc	First semester 2025	One working group session 10+ participating organisations reached	Include in the agenda of the COST CCA, WG on career advisory and support services + WG on young researchers (early 2025) NOTE: The Co-chairs of the COST Action, Nicola Dengo and Joanna Rutkowska, are both nominated by Eurodoc.
CoARA and Beneficiaries of CoARA	Sections relevant for early career researchers	Meetings of the CoARA WG for Early- and Mid-Career Researchers and Research Culture	Eurodoc	First semester 2025	One online session 20+ stakeholders (Universities, Networks, Associations etc) reached	Include in the agenda of the CoARA WG on Early and Mid Career Researchers and Research culture (early 2025).

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Mainstreaming Plan for SECURE Research Framework

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